

INTERDEPENDENCY OF WELDING SPEED AND DISTANCE BETWEEN COIL AND ROLLER DURING INDUCTION WELDING OF METAL AND GLASS FIBER REINFORCED POLYAMIDE 6

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ABSTRACT

Induction welding (IW) of metals and thermoplastic fiber reinforced polymer composites (TP-FRPC) is a promising technology for hybrid joining. It uses the possibility to induce eddy currents into a metal in order to melt the polymer of the adjacent TP-FRPC so that it adheres to the metal. By applying pressure onto both parts, e. g. with a roller following an induction coil along a weld seam, a bond can be generated. One major drawback of IW is its relatively low process speed. It is limited by the cooling (ΔT) of the welding zone between coil ($T \approx T_m + 50 \text{ K}$) and roller (welding point $T \ll T_m$). Therefore, this study investigates the influence of the distance between coil and roller on the process speed by analyzing ΔT during the welding of steel/aluminum and glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6. It was found, that the coil-to roller distance has a significant influence on the cooling ΔT at low process speeds. Moreover, an increased coil-to-roller distance can allow higher process speeds. At high process speeds, other measures, such as active cooling by an impinging air jet, must be taken.

1 INTRODUCTION

Induction welding (IW) of metals and thermoplastic fiber reinforced polymer composites (TP-FRPC) is a promising technology for hybrid joining. Since TP-FRPCs are more cost-intensive than metals and their processing suffers from a lower degree of automation, the demand for hybrid structures is growing. But these structures require joining technologies that meet the needs of TP-FRPCs. Although there are several joining methods available, they all have certain disadvantages. Mechanical fastening requires holes which damage the reinforcing fibers and drilling can lead to delamination. Adhesive bonding overcomes these problems, but often solvents and long curing cycles are necessary. Moreover, the surface of most thermoplastics is nonpolar so that they are difficult to bond. Since thermoplastics can be melted, the polymer itself can be used to adhesively bond TP-FRPCs to metals.

IW is one method to melt the polymer and is based on the ability of electromagnetic (EM) fields to transfer energy without physical contact. When an electrical conductor is placed in an alternating EM field, (generated by an induction coil) eddy currents are induced, as shown in Figure 1. According to Joule's first law, a current flowing through a conductor causes the conductor to heat up. This effect can be used to heat an electrically conductive part, such as steel or aluminum plates.

Figure 1: Eddy currents induced into a metal plate

In order to use induction heating for welding, the coil must be combined with a consolidation roller in a continuous process, as depicted in Figure 2. First, the to-be-welded metal is heated by the coil in order to melt the polymer of the adjacent TP-FRPC by heat conduction. Subsequently, the consolidation roller consolidates the welding zone by applying pressure. In addition, the roller removes energy from the welded parts. In the last step, the hybrid structure cools down.

Figure 2: Continuous induction welding process

One major drawback of IW is its relatively low process speed. It is limited by the cooling (ΔT) which occurs in the welding zone as the coil and the roller successively pass the same point. Under the coil, the temperature T in the laminate must be above the melting temperature T_m of the polymer. Usually, an offset of 50 K is considered optimal ($T \approx T_m + 50 \text{ K}$) for semi-crystalline polymers [1]. Under the roller, T must drop below T_m (welding point $T \ll T_m$) in order to create a bond without deconsolidation and voids. In recent years, the temperature distribution during continuous IW of carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics has been investigated in several studies [2]–[4]. However, no previous research on the temperature distribution during the IW process for hybrid structures is known. To fill this gap, the present study investigates the interdependency of welding speed and distance between coil and roller by analyzing ΔT .

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

In this study, two different, representative material combinations were used: first, glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6 (GF/PA6) and steel (DC01, 1.0330) and second, GF/PA6 and aluminum (AlMg3, EN-AW 5754). GF/PA6 offers sufficiently high mechanical properties and service temperature to be used for structural parts in the automotive industry. Its material properties are listed in Table 1.

	Unit	
Fibers		Roving glass
Fabric		Twill (symmetric)
Area weight	g/m^2	600
Yarn	tex	1200
Density	g/cm^3	1.8
Fiber content	% vol.	47
Thickness per layer	mm	0.5
Melting temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	220
Glass transition temperature	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	60

Table 1: Material properties of GF/PA6 [5]

Aluminum and steel are also commonly used in automotive applications. Moreover, the very different thermal and electrical properties of these two metals allow an investigation of their influence on the IW process. Steel has a lower thermal conductivity than aluminum (unalloyed steel at $100 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$: $20 \text{ W/mK} - 57 \text{ W/mK}$, aluminum alloys at $100 \text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$: 146 W/mK to 240 W/mK [6]), which leads to a more concentrated but also more uneven heating in steel plates and less heat flux to the surrounding air and tools. In addition, unalloyed steel is ferromagnetic and can therefore be heated by Joule losses and magnetic hysteresis, whereas aluminum is paramagnetic and heats only by Joule losses.

In order to determine ΔT at different process speeds and coil-to-roller distance, continuous heating experiments were performed. The temperatures in the welding zone were measured by 24 thermocouples, which were pressed into the GF/PA6 laminate with a length of 300 mm and a width of 100 mm, according to Figure 3. This plate was combined with a metal plate of the same dimensions.

Figure 3: Position and labelling of thermocouples in GF/PA plate

All welding trials were performed in a self-developed test rig. As inverter, a Power Cube 32/400 with a fixed frequency of 400 kHz was used. The coil was a double-turn pancake coil, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Left: Double-turn pancake coil, right: welding setup

In all experiments, the GF/PA6 was on top of the metal plate and the thermocouples were facing the welding zone. An additional thermocouple was added on the top side of the GF/PA6 plate at each thermocouple group (1 to 8), as shown in Figure 5, in order to identify the passing by of the roller. The stack was placed on a tool, which was moved under coil and roller. The welding process always started at thermocouple group 1.

Figure 5: Continuous heating experiment: cross section (left) and side view (right)

Welding speeds and coil-to-roller distances were varied, in order to investigate their interdependency. The distance between coil and roller is defined according to Figure 5. The power of the inverter was adjusted to the welding speed to obtain a maximum temperature in the welding zone of 170°C to 190°C. This temperature was chosen to prevent melting of the polymer which would destroy the specimen. Thus, a new specimen for each test would be required and therefore neither the exact positioning of thermocouples nor constant laminate properties could be guaranteed. No temperature control was used in order to analyze the system's response to these constant parameters.

For steel, all parameter combinations are listed in Table 2 and for aluminum in Table 3.

Welding speed in mm/s	Coil-to-roller distance in mm	Inverter power in %	Coupling distance in mm
1.8		10	
3.6		22	
5.4	55, 60, 65, 70, 80, 90, 100, 110, 120	30	6
7.2		35	
9.0		42	

Table 2: Combinations of process parameters for welding trials with steel

Welding speed in mm/s	Coil-to-roller distance in mm	Inverter power in %	Coupling distance in mm
1.08		80	
1.80		85	
2.88	55, 60, 65, 70, 80, 90, 100, 110, 120	90	3
3.60		100	

Table 3: Combinations of process parameters for welding trials with aluminum

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First, the temperatures measured during welding were used to identify the temperature distribution in the welding zone. Figure 6 shows the maximum temperatures measured by each thermocouple during welding of GF/PA6 and steel at a low (1.8 mm/s and coil-to-roller distance of 65 mm) and a high (7.2 mm/s and coil-to-roller distance of 80 mm) process speed.

Figure 6: Distribution of maximum temperatures during welding of steel and GF/PA6 at a welding speed of 1.8 mm/s, a coupling distance of 6 mm and a coil-to-roller distance e of 65 mm (1) and at a welding speed of 7.2 mm/s, a coupling distance of 6 mm and a coil-to-roller distance of 80 mm (2)

It can be observed, that a steady state is reached between approx. 110 mm and 220 mm in length direction. Caused by the uneven heating pattern, which is caused by the coil shape, and the low thermal conductivity of steel, there are still significant temperature variations during the steady state.

The distribution of maximum temperatures during the welding of GF/PA6 and aluminum is displayed in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Distribution of maximum temperatures during welding of aluminum and GF/PA6 at a welding speed of 1.08 mm/s, a coupling distance of 3 mm and a coil-to-roller distance e of 60 mm (1) and at a welding speed of 3.60 mm/s, a coupling distance of 6 mm and a coil-to-roller distance of 75 mm (2)

In this case, steady state is reached a few millimeters earlier and there is less scattering. Moreover, temperatures remain at a high level almost until the end of the plate. Aluminum heats more evenly because of its higher thermal conductivity. But (2) also shows that the desired temperature (between 170°C and 190°C) cannot be reached at higher process speeds (3.6 mm/s).

For further evaluation, thermocouple no. 6B at 210 mm, which is within steady state, was chosen. In order to analyze the suitability of a parameter combination for welding, the temperature drop ΔT between the maximum temperature T_{\max} and the temperature at the moment when the roller passes is determined. As mentioned before, a common temperature for welding is at approx. 50 K above melting temperature ($T_m + 50$ K) and therefore, $\Delta T = 50$ K is considered optimum. Graphs as shown in Figure 8 are used to analyze ΔT .

Figure 8: Heating curves of GF/PA6 and steel at different process speeds and coil-to-roller distances

In these figures, the solid black line represents the temperature in the welding zone measured at thermocouple 6B (at 210 mm in the center of the welding zone). The dashed red line is the temperature measured on top of GF/PA6. At a coil-to-roller distance of 60 mm and a process speed of 1.8 mm/s, ΔT is 33 K. Since the polymer does not melt entirely at a certain temperature but within a temperature range of 20 K to 30 K around T_m , $\Delta T=33$ K is not optimal for welding. At a reduced maximum temperature (T_m+30 K), welding could still be possible, but the quality of the joint could be affected. A doubled coil-to-roller distance (120 mm) leads to a ΔT of 70 K which is too high for welding, because the polymer would solidify before the roller has passed by. Still, an increase in maximum temperature (T_m+70 K) could make welding possible as long as the degradation temperature of the polymer is not reached. At 9 mm/s and 60 mm coil-to-roller distance, ΔT is only 8 K. It is not possible to adjust the welding process to this small ΔT , which would lead to a welding temperature of T_m+8 K in the center of the welding zone. A complete melting of the welding zone could not be guaranteed. This also applies to 9 mm/s and 120 mm with $\Delta T=13$ K. In general, it can be observed, that an increased coil-to-roller distance has a big influence on ΔT at a low welding speed (1.8 mm/s) but only a minor influence at high welding speeds (9 mm/s).

In the same way, ΔT was determined for all parameter combinations. The results are displayed in Figure 9 and Figure 10

Figure 9: Interdependency of welding speed and coil-to-roller distance for steel and GF/PA6

In these diagrams, green indicates parameter combinations, which are considered suitable for welding. Combinations which are in the yellow range can be used if the maximum temperature is adjusted to ΔT . In case of steel, welding is only possible up to 5.4 mm/s. At these process speeds, a lack of cooling can be compensated by increasing the distance between coil and roller. At higher process speeds, the slope of the straights decreases until it is almost negligible. That means that a sufficient ΔT cannot be reached.

Figure 10: Interdependency of welding speed and coil-to-roller distance for aluminum and GF/PA6

In case of aluminum, welding is only possible until 3.6 mm/s, not due to of insufficient cooling but because the induction generator is not able to heat the specimen to the defined temperature of 170°C to 190°C.

An increase in process speed always leads do a diminished influence of the distance between coil and roller on ΔT . This can be explained by calculating the additional cooling time, which can be obtained by increasing coil-to-roller distance by 1 mm for different welding speeds:

$$\text{Cooling time per mm} = \frac{1}{\text{Welding speed}} \quad (1)$$

Figure 11: Additional cooling time obtained by increasing the coil-to-roller distance by 5 mm relative to the welding speed

As mentioned before, all experiments have been performed at maximum temperatures between 170°C and 190°C in order to not destroy the specimens. The results can be applied to a process above melting temperature because the found interdependency between welding speed and distance between coil and roller will still be valid. A higher temperature will lead to a small increase of ΔT since the temperature difference between the material and the surrounding air increases.

9 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

Within this study, the interdependency of welding speed and distance between coil and roller during continuous IW of GF/PA6 with steel or aluminum was investigated. It was found, that the coil-to-roller distance has a significant influence on the cooling ΔT at low process speeds. Moreover, an increased coil-to-roller distance can allow higher process speeds. Since the distance between coil and roller can only be used for compensating an insufficient cooling at low process speeds, other measures must be taken to increase ΔT during the welding of GF/PA6 and steel for higher process speeds. One possibility is to actively cool the parts after heating them by the coil, for example by an impinging air jet or by optimizing the tooling material. In case of aluminum, the heating must be intensified. Increasing the number of coil turns as well as using a more powerful induction generator can lead to a stronger heating and thereby to a higher process speed.

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